

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

MODERN AMELIORATIVE STATE AND PROTECTION OF FERTILITY OF SOILS IN THE SHIRVAN PLAIN

Jafarova A.

AR MSE "Institute of Geography"
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-0254-209X>

Manafova A.

AR MSE "Institute of Geography"
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-0951-7893>

Guliyeva B.

AR MSE "Institute of Geography"
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18841644>

Abstract

The Kur-Araz lowland, the main farming zone of the country, has favorable climatic conditions for the cultivation of agricultural crops. However, in recent years, as in the whole world, the climatic change has shown its negative impact on both soil cover and vegetation in the Azerbaijan Republic, too and as a result, it was a reason for decrease of plant productivity in the irrigated soils. The article informed about the reclamation state and preservation of fertility of soils located in the Shirvan plain. The consequences indicated that the complex ameliorative measures should be fulfilled and the irrigation regime of agricultural crops must be correctly followed, in order to improve the ameliorative state of soils and fertility preservation.

Keywords: ameliorative, fertility, climatic changes, irrigation, salinization, soil type.

Introduction. At present, study of the soil fertility preservation and modern ameliorative state possesses an importance in providing the population with food products. The large zones of some arid places in the earth have been subjected to swamping and salinization with the application of irrigation reclamation, and as a result, the agricultural areas in the same countries lost their fertility for great unsatisfactory ameliorative state, the soil salinization process quickly developed. The unsuitable hydro-geological condition, proximity of groundwater with the high mineralization degree to the surface, the higher capillary characters of soils, intensive evaporation and high temperature stimulate intensity of the soil salinization process as a result of irrigation in these regions[6]. For this purpose researches were performed in the soils of the Zardab region and the aim was achieved.

Object and Method of the research

The experimental area was selected as a research object in the Alibayli village of Zardab which is situated in the Shirvan plain. The same soils are used under wheat and cotton plants and they cover 2.0 hectares of the zone. The sections were applied, the samples were taken and the required chemical analyses were realized according to the wide-spread method (granulometric composition, absorbed bases, pH, salt quantity, humus) by marking the coordinates of the soils in the experimental area of the characteristic places[1].

Analysis and discussion

Ameliorative state of soils is formed under the influence of natural factors and irrigation farm system. The soil cover, climate condition, geological and geomorphological structure, irrigative water, hydrological and hydro-geological level belong to the natural factors. The basic indications that characterize ameliorative state of the soils are considered salinization and

solonchification degrees, salinization type, kind, state of the soil solution, the location depth of ground-waters, mineralization degrees, a quality of the irrigative waters, the place relief, and natural and artificial drainage level of the zone.

Presence of the good climate, soil, hydro-geological condition is important for rational usage from soil for the agricultural production. Increase of soil fertility, obtaining the high and permanent agricultural products, water and heat, regulation of the food regime are possible due to the irrigation amelioration measures. The soil fertility mostly depends on water and air regimes. There should be the amount of humidity required by the plants in the soil in order to provide plants with fertility factors without interruption[2].

The Shirvan plain is situated in the Kur-Araz lowland and it is a main agricultural zone of the country. It has a good climate condition and it is mainly used under agricultural crops. The current landscape of the Shirvan plain is created due to the activity of the mountain rivers, sediments of the Kur river, and salinized rocks. The salt accumulation in groundwater and in plain soils is associated with large salts washed down from the surrounding height. The accumulative activity of the rivers flowing from the north play a main role in the creation and formation of the relief of the Shirvan plain. The flatness of the relief creates conditions for wholly irrigation of the zone and completely use of the available hydrography network[4,5]. The Shirvan plain is rich with ground-waters. The ground-waters of the zone possess unpressured and relatively free surface. The sources of water are precipitation, river water and leaking water related to irrigation[7]. The groundwater is situated near the surface because the rivers in the west part are more watery compared to the east part and the artificial irrigation is mostly used. The soil cover of the

Shirvan plain is diverse. There are bright-brown and grey cinnamonic soils in the foothill areas, bright-meadow, grey-cinnamonic soils in the debris cones of the rivers, alluvial-meadow and Tugay forest soils on the Kur bank, grey, grey-meadow and salinized soils in the east part and around parts of the debris cones. The grey-meadow soils develop in the central part of the plain, the calcareous soils develop in the depressions. The sulfate-chloride saline soils spread in the east part of the Shirvan plain, and in the debris inter-conical depressions. A quantity of salts is 3.0% and more in these soils. Geomorphology of the soils in the Shirvan plain was thoroughly studied by V.R.Volobuyev[9]. The dominant flora of the zone consists of semi-desert and dry field groupings developed in the arid climatic condition. The differentiation of soil cover happens in the main two directions – from east to west and from south to north. The Tugay forests, (qaragan-blackthorn), (qaraqan-wormwood), wormwood plant groups replace each other. The density of the total river network is 0.46 -0.5 ca/km². The density of the river network increases in connection with the growth of the precipitation from south to north, from east to west.

The Zardab region is situated in the Shirvan plain and its surface is plain, it is below ocean level. The climate is arid-field and the summer is drought semi-desert. Here, the maximum temperature is observed in summer months (41-44 ° C).There are saline, solonchak and grey, grey-cinnamonic, alluvial-meadow soils in the zone. The same soils are used under cotton, grain, wormwood and other plants. The swamps have been formed near the Ashagi Shirvan collector as a result of accumulation of surface waters in some places in the Zardab region. Restoration of the drainage canals of

which technical state isn't satisfactory is considered necessary in the same zones. The salinization process is observed in the zone soils and it shows its negative effect on productivity of the agricultural crops. Here, the structural violation is one of the main factors, it is a reason for production decrease. If this process is permanent, the ecological problems can be happened.

It is known that the salts are various in the soils of the salinized zones and they differ from one another for their toxicity. The soil classification for their saltiness degree and type was given by some scientists. V.R.Volobuyev divided the soils of the Kur-Araz lowland into soda, chloride-sodium, chloride-calcium-magnesium,sulfate-calcium, carbonate-calcium, according to their calinity [3,8].

The analysis consequences performed in the experimental soils indicated that they are clayey and heavy clayey in composition. The hygroscopic humidity in these soils is 4.25-7.19%, humus is 0.86-2.17 % at 0-100 cm of layer, a sum of the absorbed bases (at 100 gram of soil) is 22.35-29.09 mg.eq. A quantity of calcium in absorbed bases totality is dominant (44.34 - 75.47 %).A value of pH changes by 7.24 -9.0. The salt amount for dry residue is 0.119-1.053 %. CO₃ ion isn't observed in anion composition of salts, SO₄ ion is dominant Na+k (for difference) is dominant in cation composition. Generally, the soils of the experimental area are non-salinized, weakly and averagely solonetzified. The soil type was determined in the soils of the experimental area on the basis of the obtained results. The soils of the experimental area belong to are chlorine-sulfate and sulfate-chlorine for Cl:SO₄ ratio.

The salt change of soils in the experimental area was given on the following graphic.

Graphic. Change graphic of salts in the experimental soils

It should be noted that lately, the ecological changes affected ameliorative state and fertility of soils, therefore the degradation processes accelerated in

them. That's why it is important to perform large researches for improvement of the ameliorative state and fertility preservation of soils. Lately, the researches indicated that the hydro-geological ameliorative state of

the irrigated soils were noticeably improved and this was as a result of fulfillment of the purposeful ameliorative measures. [10].

Conclusions and suggestions

1. As a result of the performed researches it was determined that the soils of the experimental area are clayey and heavy clayey in composition. The soils are unsalted, weakly and averagely salinized.

2. It should be noted that the complex ameliorative measures system must be realized for improvement of modern ameliorative state and fertility preservation of soils. It is important to regulate the irrigation regime and to repair the drainage canals near the zone.

References:

1. Arinushkina E.V. Guide on chemical analysis of soils. M.,pub.MSU, 1970, p.488.
2. Aslanov H.G., Salimova V.H. The social and ecological status of the water resources use in the Great Caucasus. Baku 2018, 384p.
3. Azizov G.Z. Classification of Azerbaijan soils for their saltiness degree and type. Baku, Novruz -94, 29p.

4. Jafarova A.A. Water-temperatural regime of serozem-meadow soils in the Salyan steppe of Azerbaijan. Bulletin of Science and practice. V. 6.№3, 2020, p. 226-235

5. Jalilova L.Z. Soil salinization and productivity of agrocenoses in the Shirvan plain.LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing 2016, p.54.

6.Mammadova E.A. Ameliorative hydro-geology. Textbook for the bachelor's degree of higher school. "Laman publication polygraphy "MMC. Baku 2016, 268p.

7.Museibov M.A. –Physical geography of Azerbaijan. Pub. "Maarif". Baku, 1998, p.40

8.Rzayev M.A. Azerbaijan: Deformation and ecological durability of the irrigation agriculture. Baku 2019, "Elm ve Tehsil"(science and Education), 369p.

9.Volobuyev V.R. Soils of the Kur-Araz lowland. In the book:Soils of Azerbaijan SSR. Baku, pub. AS Azerb.SSR, Baku, 1953, p. 197-325.

10. <https://www.agro.gov.az>